

ISSN: 0975-766X

CODEN: IJPTFI

Research Article

Available Online through

www.ijptonline.com

PROCESS VALIDATION OF SIMVASTATIN 20MG TABLETS

Poonam Rana*, Pawana Mahar

Department of Pharmacy, Vivek College of Technical Education Bijnor(U.P), India.

Email:ranapoonam505@gmail.com

Received on: 10-02-2019

Accepted on: 25-03-2020

Abstract

Aim: The purpose of research was to study the process validation of simvastatin 20mg tablets to assure the quality of product. In order to meet the current regulatory requirements and to prove with assure that, product meeting its predetermined specification and quality characteristics. **Method:** the critical parameter involved in shifting, granulation, drying, blending, compression and coating stages were identified and evaluated as per validation plan. **Result:** From this result, it is inferred that the manufacturing process of simvastatin 20mg tablet will produces a product meeting its predetermined specification and quality attributes. **Conclusion:** the results of all three batches demonstrate that the manufacturing process was under control throughout all the stages, within and in between batches. Therefore the process stands validated for prospective validation study.

Key words: validation, process validation, critical process parameter, validation plan.

Introduction

The prime objective of any pharmaceutical plant is to manufacture products of requisite attribute and quality consistently, at the lowest possible cost. Although validation studies have been conducted in the pharmaceutical industry for a long time, there is an ever increasing interest in validation owing to their industry's greater emphasis in recent years on quality assurance program and is fundamental to an efficient production operation. Validation is a concept that has evolved in united states in 1978. The concept of validation has expanded through the years to embrace a wide range of activities from analytical methods used for the quality control of drug substances and drug products to computerized systems for clinical trials, labelling or process control, Validation is founded on, but not prescribed by regulatory requirements and is

best viewed as an important and integral part of cGMP. The word validation simply means assessment of validity or action of proving effectiveness. Validation is an integral part of quality assurance; it involves the systematic study of systems, facilities and processes aimed at determining whether they perform their intended functions adequately and consistently as specified. A validated process is one which has been demonstrated to provide a high degree of assurance that uniform batches will be produced that meet the required specifications and has therefore been formally approved. Validation in itself does not improve processes but confirms that the processes have been properly developed and are under control.¹

1.1 Process Validation

Pharmaceutical process validation is the most important and recognized parameter of CGMP's. It is, therefore, an element of the quality assurance programme associated with a particular product or process. "Process validation is a documented program which provides a higher degree of assurance that a specific process will produce a product meeting its predetermined specifications & quality attributes."The basic principles of quality assurance have as their goal the production of products that are fit for their intended use.²

These principles are as follows:

- Quality, safety and efficacy must be designed and built into the product.
- Quality cannot be inspected or tested into the product.
- Each critical step of the manufacturing process must be validated. Other steps in the process must be under control to maximize the probability that the finished product consistently and predictably meets all quality and design specifications.

Validation of processes and systems is fundamental to achieving these goals. It is by design and validation that a manufacturer can establish confidence that the manufactured products will consistently meet their product specifications.³

Validation should thus be considered in the following situations:

- Totally new process.
- New equipment.
- Process and equipment which have been altered to suit changing priorities.

- Process where the end-product test is poor and an unreliable indicator of product quality.

1.2 Benefits of Process Validation

1. Assurance of quality.
2. Time bound.
3. Process optimization.
4. Reduction of quality cost.
5. Minimal batch failures, improved efficiency and productivity.
6. Reduction in rejections.
7. Increased output.
8. Avoidance of capital expenditures.
9. Fewer complaints about process related failures.
10. Reduced testing in process and in finished goods.
11. More rapid and reliable start-up of new equipment.
12. Easier scale-up from development work.
13. Improved employee awareness of processes.
14. More rapid automation.
15. Government regulation (Compliance with validation requirements is necessary for obtaining approval to manufacture and to introduce new products).

1.3 Types of Process Validation

- Prospective validation
- Concurrent validation
- Retrospective validation
- Revalidation

1.3.1 Prospective Validation: Is defined as the establishment of documented evidence that a system does what it purports to do based on pre-planned protocol. This validation is usually carried out prior to the introduction of new drugs and their manufacturing process. This approach to validation is normally undertaken whenever a new formula, process or facility must be validated before routine pharmaceutical

formulation commences. In Prospective Validation, the validation protocol is executed before the process is put into commercial use. During the product development phase the production process should be broken down into individual steps. Each step should be evaluated on the basis of experience or theoretical considerations to determine the critical parameters that may affect the quality of the finished product. A series of experiments should be designed to determine the criticality of these factors. Each experiment should be planned and documented fully in an authorized protocol. All equipment, production environment and the analytical testing methods to be used should have been fully validated. Master batch documents can be prepared only after the critical parameters of the process have been identified and machine settings, component specifications and environmental conditions have been determined. It is generally considered acceptable that three consecutive batches/runs within the finally agreed parameters, giving product of the desired quality would constitute a proper validation of the process. It is a confirmation on the commercial three batches before marketing. Upon completion of the review, recommendations should be made on the extent of monitoring and the in-process controls necessary for routine production. These should be incorporated into the batch manufacturing and packaging record or into appropriate standard operating procedures. Limits, frequencies and actions to be taken in the event of the limits being exceeded should be specified. It may be possible and acceptable in particular circumstances for a manufacturer that uses the same process for several related products to develop a scientifically sound validation plan for that process rather than different plans for each product manufactured by that process.⁴

1.3.2 Concurrent Validation: It is similar to prospective, except the operating firm will sell the product during the qualification runs, to the public at its market price, and also similar to retrospective validation.

This validation involves in-process monitoring of critical processing steps and product testing. This helps to generate and documented evidence to show that the production process is in a state of control.

- In exceptional circumstances it may be acceptable not to complete a validation programme before routine production starts.
- The decision to carry out concurrent validation must be justified, documented and approved by authorised personnel.

- Documentation requirements for concurrent validation are the same as specified for prospective validation.

1.3.3 Retrospective Validation: The retrospective validation option is chosen for established products whose manufacturing processes are considered stable and when on the basis of economic considerations alone and resource limitations, prospective validation programs cannot be justified. Prior to undertaking retrospective validation, wherein the numerical in-process and/or end-product test data of historic production batches are subjected to statistical analysis, the equipment, facilities and subsystems used in connection with the manufacturing process must be qualified in conformance with CGMP requirements. The basis for retrospective validation is stated in 21CFR 211.110(b): “Valid in-process specifications for such characteristics shall be consistent with drug product final specifications and shall be derived from previous acceptable process average and process variability estimates where possible and determined by the application of suitable statistical procedures where appropriate.” Using either data-based computer systems or manual methods, retrospective validation may be conducted in the following manner:⁵

1. Gather the numerical data from the completed batch record and include assay values, end-product test results, and in-process data.
2. Organize these data in a chronological sequence according to batch manufacturing data, using a spreadsheet format.
3. Include data from at least the last 20–30 manufactured batches for analysis. If the number of batches is less than 20, then include all manufactured batches and commit to obtain the required number for analysis.
4. Trim the data by eliminating test results from noncritical processing steps and delete all gratuitous numerical information.
5. Subject the resultant data to statistical analysis and evaluation.
6. Draw conclusions as to the state of control of the manufacturing process based on the analysis of retrospective validation data.
7. Issue a report of your findings (documented evidence).

1.3.4 Revalidation: Almost all GMP texts recommend that whenever there are significant changes in the facility, equipment or process, revalidation should be carried out. The FDA process validation guidelines refer to a quality assurance system in place that requires revalidation whenever there are changes in packaging (assumed to be the primary container-closure system), formulation, equipment or processes (meaning not clear) which could impact on product effectiveness or product characteristics and whenever there are changes in product characteristics.⁶

Conditions requiring revalidation study and documentation are listed as follows:

- Change in a critical component (usually refers to raw materials).
- Change or replacement in a critical piece of modular (capital) equipment.
- Change in a facility and/or plant (usually location or site).
- Significant (usually order of magnitude) increase or decrease in batch size
Sequential batches that fail to meet product and process specification.

1.4 Phases of Process Validation

The activities relating to validation studies may be classified into three:

Phase 1: This is the Pre-validation Qualification Phase which covers all activities relating to product research and development, formulation pilot batch studies, scale-up studies, transfer of technology to commercial scale batches, establishing stability conditions and storage, and handling of in-process and finished dosage forms, equipment qualification, installation qualification, master production document, operational qualification and process capacity.⁷

Phase 2: Process validation phase (Process Qualification phase) designed to verify that all established limits of the critical process parameters are valid and that satisfactory products can be produced even under the “worst case” conditions.

Phase 3: Validation Maintenance phase requiring frequent review of all process related documents, including validation audit reports to assure that there have been no changes, deviations, failures, modifications to the production process, and that all SOPs have been followed, including change control procedures. At this stage the Validation Team also assures that there have been no changes/deviations that should have resulted in requalification and revalidation.⁸

Method of Collection of Data: The process validation of tablets manufacturing will include:-

- ❖ Identification of the process in manufacturing of tablets.
- ❖ Decision of number process runs for validation depends on the complexity of the process or the magnitude of the process. For prospective and concurrent validation, three consecutive successful production batches will be used.
- ❖ Identification of device (s) in manufacturing of tablets.
- ❖ Objective and measurable criteria in manufacturing of tablets
- ❖ Length, duration, shifts, operators, equipment in manufacturing of tablets.
- ❖ Complete description of the process.
- ❖ Any special controls or conditions to be placed on proceeding processes during the validation.
- ❖ Process parameters to be monitored and methods for controlled and monitoring.
- ❖ Product characteristics to be monitored and method for monitoring.
- ❖ Any subjective criteria like sampling, sample analysis used to evaluate the product.

Strategy for Validation of Methods

Process validation is carried out for the product of Simvastatin tablets. Consecutively 3 batches or lots were taken for process validation. All the critical parameters were evaluated for fixing the optimum process parameters for.

1. Fabrication and manufacturing of tablets

- a) Dispensing of selected materials.
- b) Sifting of API and excipients- Simvastatin, Lactose monohydrate, Microcrystalline cellulose (PH101), Pregelatinised starch maize.
- c) Sifting of excipients- Microcrystalline cellulose (PH102).
- d) Sifting of extra granular material- Magnesium stearate.
- e) Binder preparation- Citric acid, Ascorbic acid, Pregelatinised starch, IPA and BHA with purified water
- f) Optimized following parameters for fabrication-
 - Dry mixing-agitator speed, chopper speed and mixing time.
 - Binder addition- agitator speed, chopper speed and mixing time.
 - Wet mixing- agitator speed, chopper speed and mixing time.
 - Granulation- agitator speed, chopper speed and mixing time.
- g) Granulation of sifted materials in RMG.
- h) Drying in FBD.
- i) Dry material screening.

j) Blending.

k) Study of rheological properties of granules.

- Tapped Density
- Bulk Density
- Blend Uniformity

2. Compression of Simvastatin tablets.

a) In-process challenge studies: Studies such as machine speed, hopper level and hardness challenge studies were also conducted during the process.

- In machine speed challenge study, the compression machine was operated at three different speeds and the effect of these speeds on tablet properties (i.e. individual weight variation, thickness, length, hardness, friability, and disintegration time) was studied.
- In hopper level challenge study, the compression machine was operated at three different hopper levels & the effect of these hopper levels on tablet was studied.
- For study the effect of Hardness, three different levels were selected i.e.– Low, Optimum, High hardness and the effect of these hardness on tablet properties was studied.

b) Set the following parameters for compressed simvastatin tablets-

- Weight variation
- Hardness
- Thickness
- Friability
- Disintegration
- Dissolution

3. Coating of compressed simvastatin tablets.

a) Set the following parameters for coating of compressed simvastatin tablets-

- Environmental conditions
 - i. Differential pressure
 - ii. Relative humidity
- Coating parameters

- i. No of guns
 - ii. Gun to bed distance
 - iii. Nozzle size (diameter)
 - iv. Atomizing pressure
 - v. RPM of peristaltic pump
 - vi. Inlet temperature
 - vii. Outlet temperature
 - viii. Bed temperature
 - ix. Pan speed
 - x. Solution stirring
 - xi. Spray rate
 - xii. Inlet air CFM
 - xiii. Final coat weight build up (% w/w)
- Drying parameters
 - i. Inlet temperature
 - ii. Drying time
 - iii. Jogging time

4. Perform evaluation study of prepared Simvastatin tablets

- Inspection of finished product: various finished product tests were performed on tablets. The various tests were tablet inspection (appearance), assay, content uniformity, dissolution rate etc.

5. Packaging of prepared Simvastatin tablets

Material and Method

Formulation Table for Preparation of Simvastatin tablets.

S.No	Ingredients	Unit Dose(mg/tablet)
1.	Simvastatin Ph.Eur (Micronised)	40.00
2.	Lactose BP/ Ph.Eur	281.840
3.	Microcrystalline Cellulose (PH101)	12.000
4.	Pregelatinised Starch Ph.Eur	5.000
5.	Pregelatinised Starch Maize IH	30.000
6.	Ascorbic Acid BP	10.000
7.	Citric Acid (monohydrate)	5.000

8.	Purified Water	q.s.
9.	Butylate Hydroxyanisole IH	0.160
10.	Isopropyl Alcohol IH	q.s
11.	Microcrystalline Cellulose (PH102)BP	12.000
12.	Magnesium Stearate IH	4.000

PROCESS FLOW CHART

Validation Sampling Procedure.

Mfg. Stages	Sampling Stages	Tests to be performed	Approx Sample size	Acceptance Criteria
Binder preparation and granulation		Amount of binder added and methodology of addition	-	-
Drying	At the end of drying	LOD at 105 ⁰ C for 10 min		1.0-2.5% w/w
Dry screening and milling	-	Record Screen size and Mill speed	-	-
Final Blending	After final blending (15+5 min)	Blend Uniformity (Individual Assay)	3sets of 10 samples each between 100 -300 mg Sampling time after 15+5 minutes of lubrication. Quantity approx.X-3x mg (100-300 mg). Submit 3 sets for analysis, if the first set results fail to meet the specified acceptance criteria then precede for next two sets with the same acceptance criteria.	All individual values should be within ±10% of mean. Relative standard deviation (RSD) should NMT 5%
		Bulk Density Tapped Density Particle Size Distribution	Approx. 150 g of the final blend to be sampled from three different locations for physical characterization of bulk blend.	This data is being generated in house reference only and shall not have any specific acceptance criteria
Compression	Start, Middle and End of compression	Uniformity of dosage units Dissolution rate	Approx. 120 tablets at each stage Approx. 60 tablets at Least each stage.	Uniformity of dosage units Dissolution rate data shall be generated for in house reference only and shall not

				have any specific.
<u>Machine</u>	Average weight	10 tabs. at each speed		196-204 mg
<u>Speed</u>	Weight variation	10 tabs. at each speed		185-215 mg
<u>Study:</u>	Thickness	Min.20 tablets at each speed		3.20-4.20 mm
Full Speed	Hardness	Min. 20 tablets at each speed		40-130 N
Optimum Speed	Friability	6.5 g tablets/100 rev. at each speed		NMT 0.8% w/w
Low Speed	Disintegration Time	Min. 6 tablets at each speed		NMT15 min
<u>Hopper</u>	Average weight	10 tabs. at each speed		196-204 mg
<u>Study:</u>	Weight variation	10 tabs. at each speed		185-215 mg
Full level	Thickness	Min. 20 tablets at each speed		3.20-4.20 mm
Half level	Hardness	Min. 20 tablets at each speed		40-130 N
Low level	Friability	6.5 g tablets/100 rev. at each speed		NMT 0.8% w/w
	Disintegration Time	Min. 6 tablets at each speed		NMT15 min
<u>Hardness Challenge</u>	Average weight	10 tabs. at each speed		196-204mg
<u>Study:</u>	Weight variation	10 tabs. at each speed		185-215 mg
Low	Thickness	Min. 20 tablets at each speed		3.20-4.20 mm
Optimum	Hardness	Min. 20 tablets at each speed		40-130 N
High	Friability	6.5 g tablets/100 rev. at each speed		NMT 0.8% w/w
	Disintegration Time	Min. 6 tablets at each speed		NMT15 min
Coating	Dissolution rate profile	12 units dissolution rate profile	60 tablets pooled samples to be collected and submitted for analysis as specified in sampling location.	Dissolution rate profile-Not less than 75% of labeled amount of simvastatin is dissolved in 30 min

Result

All three batches were manufactured as per the batch manufacturing record. Sampling and testing in each stage was carried out as per protocol and the results of each stage are recorded.

Granulation

Equipment		Rapid mixer granulator			
S.No	Process validation	Acceptance criteria	observation		
			1 st validation	2 nd validation	3 rd validation
1	Dry mixing	Mixing time- 10min	10min	10min	10min
		Agitator speed-slow	slow	slow	slow
		Chopper speed-off	off	off	off
2	Wet mixing	Binder addition time at slow agitator speed	3min	3min	3min
		Mixing time at fast agitator speed and fast chopper speed	10min	10min	10min

Observation: - all steps during granulation were well satisfied within the specific limit.

Drying

Equipment		Fluid Bed Dryer		
Name		Observation		
Parameters	Recommendation	1 st validation	2 nd validation	3 rd validation
Air drying time (°C)	5 min	5	5	5
Inlet temperature (°C)	55-60	55-59	56-57	56-60
Outlet temperature(°C)	To be record	26-34	26-36	26-41
Drying time (min)	30 min or more till desired LOD reached to 1.0-2.5% w/w	56	60	62
Bed temperature (°C)	To be record	27-37	27-39	26-44
LOD (%w/w)	1.0-2.5 (105°C for 10 min)	1.36	1.42	1.40

Observation: - The drying activity was carried out in FBD (Fluid bed dryer) after the drying stage the pooled samples were withdrawn for LOD which will also found within the in process specification. Drying was done for at least 30 min or more till LOD achieve 1-2.5% w/w.

Blending

Equipment Name		V-Blender		
Parameters	Recommendation	Observation		
		1 st validation	2 nd validation	3 rd validation
Binder speed (rpm)	14	14	14	14
Blending time (min)	15+5	15+5	15+5	15+5

Observation: - After blending; Samples were withdrawn from 10 different locations for checking blend uniformity, assay, LOD, bulk density, tapped density and sieve analysis.

Physical characteristics of final blend:-

Parameter	Final Blend		
	1 st Validation	2 nd Validation	3 rd Validation
Weight of blend	68.31	67.25	69.12
Volume before tapping (ml)	100	100	100
Volume after tapping (ml)	79	79	81
Untapped bulk density	0.68	0.67	0.69
Tapped bulk density	0.87	0.85	0.85
Compressibility index	21	21	19

Particle size determination (PSD) of final blend:-

Sieve Size (According to B.S.S.)	% Retained		
	1st Validation	2nd Validation	3rd Validation
# 18	7.79	7.80	7.91
# 25	11.02	8.86	9.08
# 36	9.65	9.67	11.12
# 60	8.89	7.47	6.73
# 100	6.03	5.17	5.93
pan	54.78	59.84	57.20

Observation:- Whole sample comply with the specifications /meet the acceptance criteria.

Blend Uniformity

Blend Uniformity of final blend at different stages:-

S. No.	Sampling Location	Individual Assay (%Label Claim)		
		1 st Validation	2 nd Validation	3 rd Validation
1	Location-01	97.6	98.9	101.5
2	Location-02	98.1	97.8	100.0
3	Location-03	96.5	95.4	99.4
4	Location-04	97.9	95.9	97.8
5	Location-05	98.1	96.0	98.3
6	Location-06	100.8	96.6	96.8
7	Location-07	99.2	95.9	97.5
8	Location-08	101.3	96.5	96.1
9	Location-09	98.1	96.4	96.3
10	Location-10	97.3	95.9	97.5
Mean		98.5	96.5	98.1
Minimum		96.5	95.4	96.1
Maximum		101.3	98.9	101.5
%RSD		1.54	1.09	1.75

Observation: - After final blending, unit dose sample were withdrawn from 10 different locations of V-blender and Blend uniformity was checked. All the individual results were observed within the range.

Compression

Equipment Name	Tablet Compression Machine	
Punch size and shape	Upper punch	11.6×5 mm caplet shaped embossed with 's' and '3' on either side of break line
	Lower punch	11.6×5 mm caplet shaped with break line
Description	White to off white capsule shaped tablets, debossed with 's' and '3' on either side of break line on side and break line on the other side	
Parameters	Recommendation	

Avg weight (mg)	196-204
Uniformity of weight (mg)	185-215 ($\pm 7.5\%$ of avg weight)
Thickness (mm)	3.20-4.20
Hardness (N)	40-130
Friability (%w/w)	NMT 0.8 % (w/w)
6.5gm tabs/100 rev.	
Disintegration time (min)	NMT 15 min
Use of water as medium at 37\pm20C	1225-8775
Machine speed (tabs/min)	

Manufacturing process optimization

The final lubricated blend was compressed by tablet compression machine. Hopper challenge, Machine speed challenge and Hardness challenge study were performed on the three validation batches for selection of appropriate hopper level; Hardness level and machine speed for the compression of tablets, so that the tablet meets the specific requirements.

In- Process tablets characteristics at machine speed challenge Study:-

Parameters	Recommendation	Slow speed	Optimum speed	High speed
Avg weight (mg)	196-204	200.7-202.5	200.4-202.4	200.0-200.5
Uniformity of weight (mg)	185-215 ($\pm 7.5\%$ of avg weight)	191.5-207.8	192.2-209.3	191.6-207.1
Thickness (mm)	3.20-4.20	3.69-3.81	3.69-3.82	3.69-3.80
Hardness (N)	40-130	71-92	63-104	67-94
Friability (%w/w)	NMT 0.8	0.26-0.30	0.24-0.29	0.26-0.27
6.5gm tabs/100rev.	NMT 15	5:57-6:59	7:01-7:04	6:57-7:02
Disintegration time (min)	1225-8775	1250	2700	4100
Machine speed(tabs/min)				

Observation: - For the effect of compression machine speed over content uniformity three different speed levels were selected i.e- slow, optimum and high speed. As the experimental result obtained it clearly observed that there was no significant effect of machine speed over content uniformity.

In- Process tablets characteristics during hopper level challenge study:-

Parameters	Recommendation	Full hopper	Half hopper	Low hopper
Avg weight (mg)	196-204	200.4-202.4	200.2-201.0	200.3-200.4
Uniformity of weigh (mg)	185-215 ($\pm 7.5\%$ of avg weight)	192.2-209.3	192-208	192-207
Thickness (mm)		3.69-3.82	3.72-3.84	3.74-3.86
Hardness (N)	3.20-4.20	63-104	53-91	58-89
Friability (%w/w)	40-130	0.24-0.29	0.21	0.25-0.27
6.5gm tabs/100rev.	NMT 0.8			
Disintegration time(min)		07:01-07:04	06:54-06:59	06:53-06:54
Machine speed(tabs/min)	NMT 15 1225-8775	2700	2700	2700

Observation: - For the study of hopper, three different levels were selected i.e.-full, half and low hopper. As the experimental result obtained, it revealed that full hopper were selected throughout the process. Hence the parameters were found satisfactory as recommended.

In-Process tablets characteristics during hardness challenges study:

Parameters	Recommendation	Low hardness	Optimum hardness	High hardness
Avg weight (mg)	196-204	198.2-200.4	200.2-201.9	200.9-2002.1
Uniformity of weight (mg)	185-215	191.2-202.4	192-208	192-207
Thickness (mm)	($\pm 7.5\%$ of avg weight)			
Hardness (N)		3.49-3.78	3.72-3.84	3.74-3.86
Friability (%w/w)	3.20-4.20	49-94	54-96	62-108
6.5gm tabs/100rev.	40-130	0.24-0.29	0.21-0.26	0.25-0.27
Disintegration tim (min)	NMT 0.8			
Machine speed (tabs/min)		05.54-06:10	06:02-06:08	07:53-07:54
	NMT 15 1225-8775	2700	2700	2700

Observation: - For study the effect of hardness, three different levels were selected i.e. – Low, Optimum, High hardness and the effect of this hardness on tablet properties was studied. As the experimental result obtained it clearly observed that optimum hardness were selected throughout the process. Hence its parameters were more satisfactory as recommended.

Uniformity of dosage units:

Individual Assay (% Label Claim)			
Stages of compression			
S.No	START	MIDDLE	END
1	99.3	98.9	98.1
2	98.0	99.2	96.6
3	100.4	93.7	97.3
4	101.8	100.0	96.6
5	98.7	99.8	97.3
6	101.5	98.5	96.6
7	98.7	99.3	94.2
8	101.5	98.6	97.7
9	98.2	97.6	99.3
10	97.8	98.0	94.2
Mean	99.8	98.4	97.4
Minimum	97.8	93.7	94.2
Maximum	102.9	100.0	99.3
Acceptance value	4.3	4.5	4.6

Observation:-All individual value was observed within 93.7-102.9%. Maximum value observed was 4.6 against the criteria of NMT 15.

Dissolution rate profile of compressed tablets:-

S. No.	% of the labeled amount of Simvastatin is dissolved in 30 min		
Stages of compression			
	START	MIDDLE	END
1	92	93	89
2	89	90	88

3	90	92	90
4	89	91	92
5	94	92	92
6	88	92	90
Mean	90	92	90
Minimum	88	90	88
Maximum	94	93	92

Observation:

Dissolution rate data of tablet sampled at start, middle and end of compression was found satisfactory. All individual values were observed within 88-94%.

Coating of Compressed Simvastatin Tablets

Preparation of coating suspension

Parameters	Recommendation	Observation		
		1st Validation	2nd Validation	3rd Validation
Quantity of purified water taken (kg)	130.600	130.6	130.6	130.6
Quantity of Opadry20A 56532 brown taken(kg)	16.888	16.888	16.888	16.888
Stirring time of Opadry 20A 56532 brown with purified water (min)	At least for 45 till a homogenous solution is obtained	47	50	49

Prewarming of tablets				
Inlet temperature(°C)	60-80	63.9	63.2	73.6
Bed temperature(°C)	40-50	47.7	49	48.6
Pan speed	Jogging the tablets at 2 rpm every 1-2 min	Jogging the tablets at 2 rpm every 1-2 min	Jogging the tablets at 2 rpm every 1-2 min	Jogging the tablets at 2rpm every 1-2 min

Cooling of tablets after drying

Bed temperature (⁰C)	NMT 27	26.8	26.8	26.9
Pan speed (rpm)	2 rpm (slow speed)	2	2	2

Film Coating operation

No. of guns	7	7	7	7
Gun to bed distance (cm)	16-28	27	24	28
Nozzle size(diameter) (mm)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Atomizing pressure (kg/cm²)	2.5-4.5	4-4.2	4-4.2	4-4.3
RPM of peristaltic pump(rpm)	To be recorded	13.0	15	15.1
	60-80	70.6-78.3	70.4-77.5	73.8-78.2
Inlet temperature (⁰C)	40-50	50.3-53.5	48.2-54.1	52.2-54.5
Outlet temperature (⁰C)	40-55	47.9-50.2	46.0-51.0	50.3-51.6
Bed temperature (⁰C)	2-6	2.3-4.3	2-4.2	2.5-4.1
Pan speed (rpm)	Continuous	Continuous	continuous	Continuous
Solution stirring	200-600	420	500	500
Spray rate (g/min)	1000-6000	5209-5957	5052-5602	5075-5699
Inlet air CFM	1-20	10-15	10-15	15-18
Differential pressure (ΔP)	2.25-3.25	2.73	2.94	3.09
Final coat weight build up(%w/w)				

S. No.	% of the labeled amount of simvastatin is dissolved in 30 min											
	1 st validation				2 nd validation				3 rd validation			
	10min	15min	20min	30min	10min	15min	20min	30min	10min	15min	20min	30min
1	67	82	90	92	51	75	90	91	75	85	92	92
2	49	75	86	91	66	80	88	91	77	86	89	92
3	75	82	87	88	51	85	90	93	68	79	87	91
4	81	89	91	93	67	81	90	94	77	82	90	91
5	69	85	90	92	69	82	91	94	76	88	90	94
6	66	83	88	93	75	90	94	91	58	85	93	98
7	71	83	87	91	75	85	86	96	65	81	86	91
8	73	87	89	95	65	90	92	92	59	85	94	89
9	69	79	84	90	74	87	89	96	74	85	90	101
10	76	88	88	91	77	88	89	92	74	84	93	94
11	70	81	87	92	70	88	89	96	79	87	91	96
12	77	85	89	92	75	85	89	92	68	85	90	95
Mean	70	83	88	92	73	85	90	93	71	89	91	94
Min	49	75	84	88	68	75	86	91	58	79	86	89
Max	81	89	91	95	77	90	94	96	79	89	94	101

Observation: -

All steps during coating were complying with the specifications/meet the acceptance criteria. Hence all parameters were well satisfied within the specified limits. Then the coated tablets were unloaded in double polythene lined containers duly labeled for further inspection.

Dissolution rate profile of coated tablets:**Acceptance Criteria:**

NLT 80 % (Q) of the labeled amount of simvastatin is dissolved in 30 min. The dissolution rate data generated at 10, 15, 20 and 30 min for in-house references only and does not have any acceptance criteria.

Analytical Results of finished product specifications:

S.N	Parameters	Product release specification	Observation		
			1 st Validation	2 nd Validation	3 rd Validation
1	Description	Tan colored, film coated, capsule Shaped tablets, debossed with ‘s’ and ‘3’ on the either side of break line on one side & break line on the other side	Tan colored, film coated, capsule Shaped tablets, debossed with ‘s’ and ‘3’ on the either side of break line on one side & break line on the other side	Tan colored, film coated, capsule Shaped tablets, debossed with ‘s’ and ‘3’ on the either side of break line on one side & break line on the other side	Tan colored, film coated, capsule Shaped tablets, debossed with ‘s’ and ‘3’ on the either side of break line on one side & break line on the other side
2	Identification for Simvastatin Tablet				
	By HPLC	The retention time of the major peak in the chromatogram of the sample solution corresponds to that of standard solution	Complies	Complies	Complies
	By UV	The UV absorption spectrum of the sample solution must be concordant with that of standard solution.			
3	Avg weight(mg)	205.5±6.0	205.7	205.1	206.0

4	Uniformity of dosage	Meets Ph.Eur requirements	Acceptance value=5.6 (n=10)	Acceptance value=4.1 (n=10)	Acceptance value=53 (n=10)
5	LOD (%w/w)	NMT 3.0	1.6	1.7	1.7
6	Dissolution (By HPLC)	NLT 80% (Q) of the labeled amount of C ₂₅ H ₃₈ O ₅ is dissolved in 30 min	89%-102% Avg=95%	89%-94% Avg=92%	91%-95% Avg=93%
7	Microbial Limits				
	TAMC (cfu/gm)	NMT 1000	<10	<10	<10
	TYMC (cfu/gm)	NMT 100	<10	<10	<10
	E.Coli(per 1.0 gm)	Must be absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
8	Butylated hydroxyl anisole(by GC)	NMT 0.08 (NMT 100% of the quantity added)	0.04 mg (45%)	0.04 mg (46.1%)	0.04 mg (46.4%)
9	Ascorbic acid(mg/tab)	4.5-5.5 (90.0-110.0%)	4.9 98.0%	5.0 (100%)	4.8 (96.0%)
10	Citric acid monohydrate (byHPLC)(mg/tab)	2.25-2.75 (90-110.0%)	2.48 (99.0%)	2.48 (99.0%)	2.45 (98.2%)
11	Iso propyl alcohol (by GC)(ug/tab)	NMT 20	5.3	5.2	5.2
12	Relative Substance (%w/w)By HPLC				
	Methyl simvastatin	NMT 0.2	0.01	0.02	0.03
	Acetyl simvastatin	NMT 0.4	0.08	0.08	0.08
	De-hydr	NMT 0.4	0.02	0.03	0.04

simvastatin	NMT 0.4	0.30	0.28	0.29
Simvastatin Dimer	NMT 0.75	0.21	0.20	0.19
Simvastatin acid	NMT 1.0	0.57	0.56	0.56
Lovastatin & Epilostatin				
13	Assay by HPLC			
	Each film coated tablet contain			
Simvastatin Ph.Eur	19.0-21.0mg	20.5 mg	20.3 mg	20.2 mg
	(95.0- 105.0%)	102.3%	101.3%	100.8%
	Claim 20 mg			

Yield Monitoring

S. No.	Manufacturing Step	Anticipated Yield (%)	Observation		
			1 st validation	2 nd validation	3 rd validation
1	Bulk Blend	95-100	96.43	97.60	97.26
2	Compressed Tablets	93-100	94.62	95.56	95.42
3	Coated Tablets	92-100	94.62	94.54	95.18
4	Inspected Tablets	90-100	94.52	95.08	95.14
5	Final Yield	89-100	90.22	90.62	92.14

Observation: - The percentage yield obtained at various stages of manufacturing was found to be within the specified yield limit in all the three batches.

Conclusion

The validation batch of simvastatin 20mg tablets with a batch size of 450.00 kg from initial to finished product stages (finished product), were taken for evaluation to check the feasibility of manufacturing the product by process validation using the available equipment.

After evaluation of data at each validation stage and based on the outcome of results of all 3 batches of simvastatin 20mg tablets, it is concluded that simvastatin 20mg tablets meet the acceptance criteria at all the stages of manufacturing.

The finished product of all the batches complied to lay down finished product specifications and showed consistency & reproducibility within & in between batches. These results demonstrate that the manufacturing process was under control throughout all the stages, within and in between batches. Therefore the process stands validated for prospective validation study.

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Corresponding Author:

Poonam Rana*,

Email:ranapoonam505@gmail.com